

ARE YOU GOING TO WEAR YOUR WEARABLE FOR LIFE? DESIGNING FOR LONG-TERM SOCIAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a Model from which to develop design principles for products and services that promote long-term positive health and wellbeing. This Independency Model (IM) attempts to explain users' varying levels of dependent behavior and ways they can change that behavior. As a journey toward self-reliance, these behaviors represent failures in sustainable change partly due to short-term thinking, loss of impulse control or lack of positive feedback. Design principles for products and services should differ with each profile in order to best help people evolve to tech independence. While persuasive technologies, such as wearable activity trackers, aim to help people induce and adhere to healthy behaviors by tracking their status, creating awareness and giving action plans, they do not necessarily offer any "exit" strategies. This new model encourages products and services to be designed for people to "graduate" from the profile that is dependent on technologies, and internalize such independent healthy habits as their own.

KEY WORDS: *Persuasive technology, human behavior change, wearable devices, technology independence, internalized behavior.*

INTRODUCTION

There are a variety of wearable activity trackers that are designed with persuasive technologies, attempting to modify people's health-related behaviors, such as exercise, posture, heart rate, sleep patterns, emotional health and nutrition. These devices aim to promote healthy behaviors by providing constant reminders, encouragements and status awareness. However, many people disengage and/or discontinue the use of those devices and withdraw from healthy habits. Ledger et.al. (2014) suggest that more than half of U.S. consumers who have owned a modern activity tracker no longer use it. A third of U.S. consumers who have owned these devices stopped using them within six months of receiving them [1]. Although there is little evidence available to assess how their behavior has changed after they stop using such devices, most of them have likely relapsed into the state they were in prior to owning the devices.

There are, however, a number of studies showing enhanced utilization because of built-in feedback triggered by behavior patterns. Pina et. al. (2012) developed Fitbit +, that detects when people have been inactive in their work environment

for a long time and then prompts them to take a short break from their desks [2]. While there are several other systems that offer the same type of reminder function, such systems often propose cues at inconvenient times [2], cause cost or annoyance and fall into subsequent non utilization. BJ Fogg (2009) introduced the FBM model which suggests that for a person to perform a target behavior, he or she must (1) be sufficiently motivated, (2) have the ability to perform the behavior, and (3) be triggered to perform the behavior [3]. This model provides a solid theoretical and methodological foundation for designers of persuasive experiences to design artifacts that effectively trigger target behaviors.

However, the system design does not incorporate a pattern of exiting device usage and internalizing healthier behaviors on the consumer's own volition.

This paper introduces the Independency Model (IM), a conceptual model that classifies four different user profiles based on two factors; self-regulation capability and source of self-validation reference. This model identifies what types of supports are needed for people who fall into each quadrant in order to migrate into the independent profile. These user profiles can be viewed as phases that users go through,

where the activity tracking device plays an effective role, but only as a waypoint towards an independent healthy lifestyle without relying on tracking devices.

DISCUSSIONS

The Independency Model (IM)

The IM can be described as a 2x2 matrix [Figure 1] with an attribute of self-regulation capability; High or Low and an attribute of source of self-validation reference; Internal or External. On the vertical axis, self-regulation refers to a person's capacity for altering their behavior. It greatly increases the flexibility and adaptability of human behavior, enabling people to adjust their actions to a remarkably broad range of social and situational demands. It has four subcomponents: standard, monitoring, willpower and motivation to meet the standard (Baumeister et.al. 2007) [4]. High on the axis means high self-regulation capabilities, whereas low on the axis indicates a low capability of altering behavior. In the context of health related behavior, people categorized in the upper two quadrants are relatively good at maintaining regular exercise, healthy eating and sleeping habits. On the horizontal axis, self-validation refers to how and where a person receives information about his or her identity or who he or she is as a person. The right side represents "Internal Validation," referring to a person who is confident in their internal belief system and relies on their own self-awareness to make decisions.

Developing "Internal Validation" requires the definition of values and goals for oneself and then following through on them. For example, a person who doesn't care about how he appears to others on Facebook, states what he believes regardless of the number of likes. The left side represents "External Validation"; that is, a person prone to seek the approval and admiration of others to feel a sense of value. In the Facebook example, this is a person who looks to others and changes his behavior based on how his status will increase. External validation can be unpredictable and temporary as the person in that category is, in most cases, unable to control the validation. So behavior induced by external validation is likely to be ad hoc and not sustainable in the long run.

In this 2 x 2 matrix [Figure 1], the upper right quadrant is the "Independent" profile, which is the final destination recommended in the Model. The lower left quadrant is the "Submissive" profile, from which departure is encouraged. Thus, either via lower right quadrant, which represents the "Tension" profile or upper left quadrant, which represents the "Limit" profile, the person will arrive at the "Independent" profile.

The "Tension" profile, lower right quadrant, refers to someone who has Internal Validation, but has low capability of Self-Regulation. People who fall in this profile are earnest enough to set up their high-level principles, values and beliefs, but they often fail to follow them. This Model attributes this failure to vague standards of effective monitoring to ob-

Figure 1. Independency Model

jectively know how they are doing. This provides insufficient energy to sustain their willpower and fails to motivate them to meet a high standard. While this type of persona has internal approval, they have high expectations of themselves and they constantly have to deal with a certain degree of guilt and shame. They frequently struggle internally, and go back and forth between working hard and feeling a sense of failure.

The "Limit" profile, upper left quadrant, refers to someone who seeks External Validation, and has a high capability of Self-Regulation. People who are categorized in this profile have resources to control themselves and are good at adhering to a desired habit once the goal is clearly articulated. They can autonomously create plans and milestones to achieve their goal and follow the path they establish. "Limit" profiles have an effective way to monitor their progress and know how to maintain their energy level to keep going. However, since they are highly dependent on obtaining approval and endorsement from others, they are susceptible to authority or trends. In this regards, they can be dependent on wearable devices, which act as external validation. If not device specific, then social media re-affirmation plays an important role. Because of accessibility, broad usage and immediacy, it has become increasingly easier to obtain external validation through social media. Research suggests that this dependency pushes people towards addictive online usage and external validation is one important factor relating to this (Young 1998, Griffiths 2000, Song et. al. 2004). [5][6][7] In the context of health and wellbeing, achieving temporary goals is part of a positive strategy for some, but the key is continuous re-evaluation working toward longer-term sustainable goals.

The "Independent" profile, upper right quadrant, refers to people who are independent and in control of constant physical activities, healthy sleep and food intake habits. They care about totally balanced mind and body health. They have their own lasting principles about quality of life that is based on human interaction, thus are not influenced by short-term

trends and fashion. They know all about the latest technologies and open to try them, but won't succumb to the lure of tech dominance over human or physical interaction. They are also socially and intellectually active and emotionally mature so that their healthy habits rarely run into conflict with occupational, social, family or community obligations.

The "Submissive" profile, lower left quadrant, refers to people who are dependent on external validation and have a low capability of self-regulation. This is the most challenging group to motivate as it requires an "entrance" strategy. Post "entrance," these consumers must choose a path either through "Tension" or "Limit" to get to "Independence."

Design principles for each profile to help move toward Independence

Among these four different profiles, "Tension" and "Limit" are typically current users of wearable activity tracking devices [Figure 2]. "Submissive" is the least preferable profile and a path of departure from this profile is strongly encouraged, "Independent," "Tension" and "Limit" are the groups for which wearable activity tracking devices certainly assist to great advantages. However, long-term goals of stable change and internalization of healthy habits, require a built-in approach toward Independence.

For "Submissive" types: an entrance strategy is needed as they are not willing to try to make changes in their lives. This modification of behavior may require a single shocking trigger. However, a trigger may create an unnecessary distraction. - (Fogg, 2009). Since this profile shows no movement by simply being presented their current habits and goal settings, there are two ways to measure the change in their behavior. One is to entice them by visualizing a positive future so that they can see themselves post-effects as being more admired and respected. This increases the likelihood to evolve to the "Limit" profile, whereby people also value external vali-

dations. Another path is to show a negative consequence, which is the brutal result of long-term unhealthy behavior. This will likely drive them to adopt the "Limit" or "Tension" behavior.

For "Tension" types: while struggling and bouncing around, this profile seeks a balanced approach to life. Wearable activity tracking devices push the user to set achievable goals while heavily emphasizing support through quick positive motivational encouragement. This reminder model works to motivate people into a more active encounter. The key is that the reminder has to be contextualized and appear at the perfect time. Therefore, these cues require intelligence and behavior monitoring, which is highly context sensitive based on schedule, work status and psychological state of the users.

For "Limit" types: those in the "Limit" profile have always had an easy time setting their own boundaries. They are often the ones setting controls. Given their reliance on external standards for appropriate behavior, they respond well to coaching input. A coach offers personal motivation to help him/her to accomplish a specific target. This method assumes the person will continue with the practice he/she learned (which is most often the case with these pleaser personalities). Short-term goals, however, have to be quickly translated to long-term goals. By showing long-term effects of negative behavior, the "Limit" profile can be encouraged to take a longer view toward a healthy lifestyle. The goal has to be a higher level and superordinate. Superordinate level goals are thought to contribute to a more profound and lasting motivational experience than focal-level goals [8]. Because superordinate goals reflect the principles that individuals value [8], researching these higher-level goals may show how exercise fits into an individual's greater life objectives and their personal goal structures [9].

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STUDY

Although still in its early and conceptual phase, the Independence Model (IM) provides a comprehensive view of people's health related behavior primarily in the context of wearable tracking device usage. It suggests a path to liberate people from their dependency of these devices. [Figure 3.] This is what we encourage those designing these products and services do in order to secure the long-term health of their users. True independence or a holistic healthy life state requires that technology invite people to recognize current behavior and internalize healthier habits rather than relying on permanent usage of such technological devices. This is an initial proposal for further study. The effectiveness of each design criteria and detailed mechanism and path for people to eventually graduate to Independence is yet to be fully researched both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Figure 2. Wearable activity tracking devices can be helpful "Tension" and "Limit" profiles

Figure 3. Two alternate paths to "Independent". A wearable device should employ both "Entrance" and "Exit" strategies

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